

NUMERICAL MODELING AND OPTIMIZATION OF PEROVSKITE SOLAR CELLS USING SCAPS-1D

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ABSTRACT

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The perovskite solar cells (PSCs) is emerging thin film photovoltaic technology with power conversion efficiency (PCE) of 27% exceeding conventional Si solar cells. Organic-inorganic perovskites are widely used in photovoltaic applications due to their favorable bandgap, optoelectronic properties and easy of fabrication process. Herein we numerically optimize the device parameters such as layers thickness, doping density, series and shunt resistance of PSCs using solar cell simulator capacitance software (SCAPS-1D). The optimized simulated device shows maximum PCE of 27.37%, fill factor (FF) of 83.12%, current density (J_{sc}) of 26.5 mA/cm² and open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) of 1.19 V. The optimized values of the device SnO₂ electron transport layer (ETL) thickness, perovskite absorber layer, hole transport layer (HTL), perovskite defect density, doping concentration of absorber layer, series resistance (R_s) and shunt resistance (R_{sh}) were recorded as 5 nm, 950 nm, 200 nm, 1×10^{12} , 1×10^{16} , $1.4 \Omega \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and $10^8 \Omega \text{ cm}^{-2}$ respectively. These findings suggest the importance of device parameters and their optimization for practical application in device fabrications of efficient and stable PSCs.

INTRODUCTION

The need for power is constantly growing. To avoid catastrophic environmental damage, it is important to think about cheap, clean, and flexible energy options. Solar energy is an awesome and cost-effective environmentally friendly energy source with numerous potential applications. Perovskite solar cells (PSCs) are a promising option for

affordable and environmentally friendly photovoltaics with achieved PCE of 27% within the last two decades [1]. As compared to silicon solar cells, perovskite solar cells have engrossed more interest due to their frequent development in power conversion efficiency (PCE) [2]. The parameters for its fast growth are high charge mobility, direct band gap and extensive carrier diffusion length. There are several

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architects of perovskite solar cells including single and triple junctions and perovskite tandem [2,3]. In a typical PSCs, the perovskite works as an absorber layer, is sandwiched between charge transport layers i.e electron ETL and HTL. The energy level alignment of ETL and HTL with absorber layer provides ground for effectual transportation of charges towards the corresponding electrodes [4,5]. The charge transport layer plays vital role for efficient and stable PSCs. Among the available electron transport layers, the SnO₂ and TiO₂ are widely used for a planner and mesoporous architecture of PSCs. The SnO₂ as ETL has major advantages over TiO₂ due to its under UV stability, higher electrical conductivity and suitable optical band gap [5]. Furthermore, several organic and inorganic materials for HTL have been used; however, Spiro-OMeTAD is most prominent to attain maximum PCEs. The transportation of holes from the perovskite layer to the electrode and transportation of electron from perovskite layer to cathode is supervised by HTL and ETL respectively. The extraction of electrons from the perovskite layer is done by ETL and holes are also blocked by ETL [6]. In comparison to a perovskite layer, the lowest unoccupied molecular orbit (LUMO) of the conduction band in the electron transport layer ought to be less. Although, for the control of transportation of holes the highest occupied molecular orbit (HOMO) of valence band must be intense. One of the hurdles in commercializing the perovskite layer is low electron mobility and instability of TiO₂ as an ETL in UV exposure [7]. To address this issue, SnO₂ and ZnO are being used as ETL in PSCs [7].

SnO₂ has high electrical conductivity as well as high electron mobility. optical bad gap is 3.6-4.0 eV, which increases its significance [7-11]. However, different types of defects exist in the layer and at the perovskite interfaces which cause low rates of electron extraction. It also becomes the reason for charge recombination which boosts the series resistance and makes device instable [12]. However, combining the insights garnered from experimental data with the capability of numerical simulations is essential to completely appreciate and investigate the device's performance. This research seeks to understand the complex behavior of solar power cells made of perovskite by combining the experimental results and numerical analysis of the PSCs. We intensively investigated the effect of each layer thickness, carried density effect of absorber layer and series and shunt resistance effect on the device performance.

METHODOLOGY

The numerical simulation techniques used in this study played a fundamental role in augmenting our understanding for perovskite solar cells (PSCs) by providing valuable insights into their optoelectronic properties and device

behavior. This synopsis provides a description of the numerical simulation techniques employed, including device physics simulations, optoelectronic simulations, and the software or tools utilized.

Device architecture

For the perovskite solar cell structure, we used an indium doped tin oxide (ITO) substrate, SnO₂ as an ETL, Perovskite as an absorber layer and Spiro-OMeTAD as a HTL. Perovskite absorber layer is sandwiched between ETL and HTL followed by Au as metal back contact as shown in figure 1.a.

The band energy alignment of the perovskite absorber layer with ETL and HTL is aligned such that the photogenerated charges are extracted on towards the corresponding charge layer as shown in figure 1.b.

Figure 1: (a) Planner Perovskite solar cell architecture and (b) Band energy alignment of Perovskite absorber with charge transport layers.

Parameter	ITO	SnO ₂	Perovskite	HTL
Thickness (μm)	0.400	0.030	0.500	0.100
Bandgap (eV)	3.5	3.93	1.50	3.200
Electron affinity (eV)	4.59	4.59	3.93	2.100
Dielectric permittivity	9	9	10	3.000
CB effective density of states (cm ⁻³)	2.2 × 10 ¹⁸	2.2 × 10 ¹⁸	1 × 10 ¹⁸	2.5 × 10 ¹⁸
VB effective density of states (cm ⁻³)	1.8 × 10 ¹⁹	1.8 × 10 ¹⁹	1 × 10 ¹⁸	1.8 × 10 ¹⁹
Electron thermal velocity (cm/s)	1 × 10 ⁷	1 × 10 ⁷	1 × 10 ⁷	1 × 10 ⁷
Hole thermal velocity (cm/s)	1 × 10 ⁷	1 × 10 ⁷	1 × 10 ⁷	1 × 10 ⁷
Electron mobility (cm ² /Vs)	200	200	200	2 × 10 ⁻⁴
Hole Mobility (cm ² /Vs)	50	50	50	2 × 10 ⁻⁴
Shallow uniform acceptor density NA (cm ⁻³)	–	–	1 × 10 ¹⁶	1 × 10 ⁷
Shallow uniform donor density ND (cm ⁻³)	1 × 10 ¹⁸	1 × 10 ¹⁸	0	–
Defect Density (cm ⁻³)	1 × 10 ¹⁸	1 × 10 ¹⁵	1 × 10 ¹²	1 × 10 ¹⁸

Table 1: Properties of layers used in perovskite solar cell for SCAPS-1D simulation.

Device physics simulations

Drift-diffusion models: These simulations employ continuity equations, combined with charge transport and recombination mechanisms, to investigate the behavior of charge carriers within PSCs. Finite element method (FEM): FEM simulations solve partial differential equations to simulate carrier transport, electric field distribution, and charge recombination processes in PSCs devices. Further, Software/tools: SCAPS-1D can be used for the simulation of PSCs. By varying parameters such as thickness, electron affinity, band gap, electron and hole mobility, and work function, the parameters of PSCs such as PCE, FF, J_{SC} and V_{OC} can be recorded. SCAPS software works on two equations which are passion equations (1) and electron, hole continuity equation (2, 3).

$$\frac{d^2}{dx^2} \Psi(x) = \frac{e}{\epsilon} [p(x) - n(x) + N_D - N_A + \rho_p - \rho_n] \quad (01)$$

$$\frac{dj_p}{dx} = G - R \quad (02)$$

$$\frac{dj_n}{dx} = G - R$$

The e is the charge of an electron, Ψ is electrostatic potential, ϵ is dielectric constant, n and p and n are the electron and holes concentration, N_D denotes the donor density, N_A acceptor density, ρ_n and ρ_p are the electrons and holes distribution, J_p is the hole current density, J_n is the electron current density, G represents the carrier generation rate and R is the recombination rate.

SCAPS has the capability to manage constant illumination, which can be achieved through either monochromatic light or by employing default standard spectra such as AM 1.5 G and AM 1.5D. The simulation can restrict the wavelength range to replicate the application of filters that allow only long-pass or short pass light. Additionally, a "small signal" illumination can be introduced to mimic spectral response measurements. A universally applied exponential absorption law, defined by user-specific parameters, is assumed for all semiconductor layers^[13].

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The device simulation is carried out in SCAPS-1D software using the given parameters in table1. Comparison and numerical studies are performed for the perovskite solar cell. The layer thickness of SnO_2 as an electron transport layer, MAPbI_3 as a perovskite absorber and Spiro-OMeTAD as an HTL are as shown in figure 2(a,b,c) respectively.

I-V curves of simulated device:

The I-V curve obtained for the simulated results of PSCs shown in figure1 is based on the structure ITO/ SnO_2 /perovskite/Spiro-OMeTAD /Au obtained from the previous results^[5,10]. The maximum achieved PCE of the device is 27.37%. The I-V curves obtained is based on the SnO_2 ETL thickness of 5 nm, Perovskite thickness of 900 nm, and HTL thickness 200 nm.

Figure 2: I-V curves the simulated results of PSCs.

Effect of ETL layer thickness:

The ETL layer plays vital role in extracting photoexcited electrons from the absorber layer. The device parameters such as PCE, FF, J_{SC} and V_{OC} are recorded for the SnO_2 ETL thickness between 1 nm to 100 nm. The optimum SnO_2 ETL thickness is set to be around 5 nm. With increase in the ETL thickness, PCE and FF rapidly decrease. Whereas the J_{SC} and

V_{OC} decrease slightly. This is attributed to increase in materials resistance, which causes decrease in electron flow within the material, and hence, J_{SC} , FF and PCE reduces.

Figure 3: Simulated results of SnO_2 ETL layer thickness and its effect on device performance.

Effect of perovskite layer thickness:

The perovskite absorber layer thickness directly influences the device's performance. The perovskite layer thickness is set from 50 nm to 1000 nm and recorded the device performance. The PCE, J_{SC} and V_{OC} increase rapidly with increase in perovskite layer thickness. Whereas the FF increases linearly up to 400 nm. The optimum layer thickness for the perovskite absorber layer is recorded between 550 to 600 nm with device PCE over 25%, FF 82.6%, J_{SC} 26.3 mA/cm^2 and V_{OC} 1.91 V. This optimum layer thickness is also well in agreement with our experimental results [5].

Figure 4: Simulated results of perovskite absorber layer thickness and its effect on device performance.

Effect of HTL layer thickness:

The HTL layer is used to extract the holes from the absorber layer. Along with a proper band energy alignment of HTL, layer thickness also needs optimization for an efficient device. Here we set the HTL layer thickness from 25 nm to 400 nm for the numerical analysis of efficient device. The

device PCE, J_{SC} and V_{OC} increases with increase in HTL layer thickness. Whereas the FF of the device decreases as the layer HTL thickness is over 50 nm. This decrease in the FF is attributed to the bulk recombination and interfacial recombination in the device. The optimum layer thickness for the HTL layer is recorded between 100 nm to 200 nm is in close agreement with experimental results.

Figure 5: Simulated results of HTL layer thickness and its effect on device performance

Effect of R_s and R_{sh} on device performance:

The series resistance (R_s) and shunt resistance (R_{sh}) also influence the device performance. We obtained efficient device performance with varying R_s and R_{sh} between 12 $\Omega \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and $101 - 10^{10} \Omega \text{ cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The optimum values of R_s and R_{sh} obtained for an efficient device are 1.4 $\Omega \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and over $10^8 \Omega \text{ cm}^{-2}$ respectively. With increase in R_s values, the decreases due to increase in the materials resistance and hence bulk recombination in the device.

Figure 6: The contour plot between R_{sh} and R_s for optimized device.

CONCLUSION

This study reports the numerical analysis of perovskite solar cell with optimized device parameters such as ETL, perovskite absorber and HTL layers thickness, defect density, perovskite doner density, R_s and R_{sh} using SCAPS simulation. The modulated device of structure ITO/

SnO₂/Perovskite/Spiro-OMeTAD/Au showed PCE of 27.37% and FF over 83% using optimized ETL, perovskite and HTL layer thickness of 5 nm, 900 nm and 200 nm respectively. The study also indicates SnO₂ as a promising ETL and Spiro-OMeTAD as HTL for a perovskite of bandgap of 1.5 eV. Hence these results indicates that further improvement in device PCE is possible for the simplest PSCs structures simulated.

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